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Learning model for handball sports education

Abstract: The model used in this study is research and development. This proposal is clearly inspired by age-appropriate, game-appropriate and action-oriented didactic models and includes cross-references to the current state-of-the-art of teaching concepts for the sport games as well as to the Bulgarian curriculum for the subject “physical exercise and sports”. This methodological approach can develop aspects of motor skills, mental skills, social skills, emotional stability, etc. The aspects developed in this way will have a positive effect on a proper and healthy lifestyle by introducing selected physical activity. In the last few years, we have been developing different concepts to make handball in school even more attractive and interesting, for example, by offering special measures for training physical education teachers or developing teaching materials and concepts for different age groups. One of the goals of sports education is to increase the popularity of sports games and to attract more athletes, especially in our case of handball. Games are called modified because they represent a dilute, modified form of the main game. They can be competitive or collaborative and are recommended at any level of education. An important aspect in this context is the position of handball as part of physical education in schools and relevant institutions such as universities, colleges and others. The principles of teaching are: modernity, adaptation to social and cognitive abilities of the student, relevance and sustainability of knowledge. Establishment of the basic course of motion handball learning through sport education model is expected to give a clear picture of the differences between conventional learning with the learning of athletic competition. The sports educational model is also oriented to direct student involvement through competitions in handball as part of the educational program.

Keywords: learning handball, sports education model, development, technical skills, sport.

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Обучителен модел за спортно образование по хандбал

Резюме: Използваният модел в това проучване е изследване и развитие на играта хандбал, а принципите на преподаване са: модерност, адаптация към социалните и когнитивните способности на ученика, уместност и устойчивост на знанията. Това предложение е ясно вдъхновено от подходящи за възрастта и ориентирани към действие дидактически модели, като включва препратки към текущото състояние на преподаваните концепции за спортни игри, както и към учебна програма на МОН за предмета „Физическо възпитание и спорт”. Този методически подход може да развие аспекти на двигателни умения, умствени умения, социални умения, емоционална стабилност и др. Разработените по този начин аспекти ще имат положителен ефект върху правилния и здравословен начин на живот, чрез въвеждане на избрана физическа активност. През последните няколко години разработихме различни концепции, за да направим хандбала в училище още по-привлекателен и интересен, чрез предлагане на иновативни методи за обучение по физическо възпитание и разработване на учебни материали за различни възрастови групи. Една от целите на спортното образование е да повиши популярността на спортните игри и да привлече повече спортисти, особено в нашия случай за спорта хандбал. Тези игри ние наричаме модифицирани, защото представят видоизменена форма на основната игра. Те могат да бъдат конкурентни или съвместни и се препоръчват на всяко ниво на образование. Важен аспект в този контекст е позицията на хандбала като част от физическото възпитание в училищата и съответните образователни институции като университети и колежи. Предлагайки този обучителен модел по хандбал, очакваме да дадем ясна картина за разликите между конвенционалното обучение и иновативния формат. Като цяло спортно-образователният модел е насочен към обучението на учениците от 3-ти до 12-ти клас, като част от образователната програма по хандбал.

Ключови думи: обучение в хандбал, модел на спортно образование, развитие, технически умения, спорт.

Introduction

The purpose of this research is to develop the basic course of handball through sport education model. The process of learning in basic subjects is still ongoing sports movement conventionally. This means that learning patterns are still centered on the teacher with the delivery of basic techniques that separate sports from sports games.

Basic course handball motion is one of the subjects being taught the game at Faculty of Sport. Characteristics handball very dynamic game such as basketball and football games. During this basic course handball motion submitted through practice approach to the delivery of basic techniques of sport that is often separate from the actual game atmosphere. Where do the game, the game does not conform with the nature of students' ability and loss of values. Moreover, the learning process does not provide a complete experience on the students in the exercise. It is considered incompatible with the concept of developmentally Appropriate practices. Even in reality, for most students in this way less actively involve students. In order to go beyond the traditional approach to teaching, we propose to practice modified sports games in handball teaching, which are based on the approach to understanding the games in which each of the students can participate in the decision-making process. Teaching progresses through game tactics instead of technical skills (*Varbanov et al., 2005*). This approach offers real opportunities for children to develop their own games, thus participating in their own learning. They share ideas, work collaboratively and naturally discover why rules are important and their goals.

Based on preliminary studies, it is known that the basic competencies of the syllabus content of basic subjects hand ball motion is as follows:

- 1) understand the history, position, technique and basic tactics, handball rules,
- 2) understand and demonstrate the form of heating handball,
- 3) know and demonstrate basic techniques of dribbling, passing, and shooting,
- 4) know the game of handball,
- 5) perform three basic tests handball game (*Hörtsch, 2003*).

Children need to adapt to the stage of development in order to form a student's intellect capable of acting in his own environment (*Rinck & Guerrero, 1997*). The assessment of the perceptual elements of the behavior itself and of its tactical thinking is a convenient moment to eliminate the exclusively mechanical training, through which behaviors are developed that are too automated. To this end, the teacher should facilitate the offering of conditions for variable performance in games, alternating with periods of shorter and less fixed repetitions. All these positive aspects and forms of improving handball education, over time, lead to socially acceptable behavior in everyday life. This is the vital, educational aspect of the handball game (*Schubert, 2007*).

Goal and objectives of the training

The goal is to help teachers of physical education and sports to interact with pedagogical methods for teaching the sport of handball in certain levels of education.

The objectives are:

- development of the basic course of handball knowledge and skills through a sports-educational model.
- the methods used should be in accordance with the age and physical development of the students.

It is known that the ability to move depends on the development of the central nervous system, following a specific pattern, the process being influenced by what the senses are exposed to. There is a close connection between the development of your perception and your motor functions, and this development also follows a specific pattern. Development can happen fast or slow. Children develop at different rates even at the same age. Children start school with the ability to move in “conventional movements” such as crawling, walking, running, jumping, throwing and climbing (*Dimkova, 2019*).

At the age of 7 to 10 the main focus should be on fun, enjoyment and a sense of achievement, with competition playing only a minor role (*Siedentop & Hastle, 2004*).

Results, scores and rankings may induce an improper performance-orientation. It would be desirable to keep the game as non-physical as possible to allow the technical skills to unfold undisturbed. Rules may have an adverse effect on the flow of the game, therefore only the most elementary guidelines should be developed on the basis of concrete situations that may arise during a game. “Play on your own and play against friends” might be the motto at this age – go for experience rather than results! In practice, minihandball is by nature almost exclusively a game played for the sake of playing. It is only at the end of this development phase that children start enjoying competitive playing.

A prerequisite for the development of motor functions is that children have been exposed to as many experiences as possible. The central nervous system, which controls movement, is already fully developed at the age of 10 to 12 years (*Hörtsch, 2003*).

We will get acquainted with established facts based on reliable research:

- during its development the child goes through periods of rapid growth (height) and slow growth (perceptions) growth occurs (height and perceptions) just before puberty.
- girls usually develop earlier than boys;
- muscle strength increases about 1 year after the onset of puberty;
- at the age of 10 to 12 the child is able to learn tactical and technical skills;
- endurance training and coordination may be less effective during puberty.

The child's development is of course the product of various factors (motor functions, mentality, language of communication, senses and thoughts) (*Kurikulum. Kurikulum Fakultas Ilmu Keolahbagaan UNY, 2002*).

As a consequence of the above facts/prerequisites, it is recommended that when teaching handball in school, technical and tactical skills in different age categories be taken into account. How to make this development suitable for our students, we can understand in our proposed training model.

Important guidelines in the teaching of handball for 3-4 grade

- Allow children to explore how objects move and how they manipulate.
- The practice should include the following motor skills that are directly related to team handball: running, jumping, starting, stopping, changing direction, landing, jumping, pushing, catching and passing, throwing and balancing the body.
- Early success is important, so be sure to give specific praise and create activities that are progressive but at the same time appropriate to the children's ability level.
- Make activities fun.

Important guidelines in the teaching of handball for 5-6 grade

- Activities should be designed to include exercises for flexibility, muscle strength, endurance and various fitness exercises.
- Focus on developing the following skills: speed running, reversing, controlled starting and stopping, landing and rolling – to prevent injury, shooting at the door, two-handed skipping, bouncing an object in the flying phase overhead or below the waist or above the shoulder, when it involves the movement or dribbling of the ball.
- Focus on teamwork and collaboration, not competition.
- They must use a ball that is the right size for their age and abilities.
- When creating performance workouts for students, plan for them to be short-lived but active, simulated by play situations, and require all children to move.
- Students should also be familiar with the concepts of attack and defense. In particular, to find and use open space, it is good to create a situation with a numerical advantage (2:1), (3:2).

Important guidelines to know for grades 7-8

- Exercises and practices should have aerobic and anaerobic work. Also include flexibility and muscle strength.
- Basic skills mentioned in the sections of earlier classes need to be reinforced and refined in real play.
- It is important to minimize competitiveness by emphasizing teamwork, cooperation and sports and technical skills.
- Students at this level should also be familiar with the mechanical structure of skills and that applying this structure will lead to a better ability to move. Elements to stress include taking a ready position, absorbing landing force, performing deceptive movements (attack-position), and following the smooth transfer of momentum.
- Review the concept of purpose, the importance of floor marking, and the use of a ball appropriate to the students' ability level.
- The rules of the game must be learned, and each element of the game must be entered correctly and accurately.
- Use short, active workouts that simulate situations with games and keep all students active.
- Some offensive and defensive strategies that can be introduced at this level include 1:1, 2:2, 3:3, in which the player with the ball moves, by dribbling with the ball, until the player is released to receive. The player without the ball moves freely in space to be available for receiving a pass, defensive strategies from person to person, zonal concepts in which the defender maintains his position between the attacker and the target (*Rachman & Susanto, 2005*).

Important guidelines in the teaching of handball for grades 9-10

- The activities are designed to include cardiovascular endurance, muscle strength and flexibility.
- Continue to upgrade basic skills and strategies in the game situation. Tactics can be taught as an extension of skills.
- Students can be introduced to specific, special positions and take on greater responsibilities in the team.
- The mechanics of the basic movement continues to be applied and practiced with increased speed and intensity.
- Use standard targets, balls and markings, if available.
- All rules of the game must be followed.
- Increase offensive and defensive strategies and introduce situations with special games.
- Enter goalkeeper techniques.

Important guidelines in the teaching of handball for 11-12 grades

- Continue to emphasize all the fitness concepts introduced in the earlier sections.
- Specify specialized positions.
- Continue to develop team unity and team tactics.
- Increasing independence in individual training and sophistication skills.
- Skills development should begin where and when appropriate.

How this product relates to current educational thinking

Depending on the level of development of the group, use more of the following elements when evaluating student learning at the end of the year.

1. Have students create their own modified rules that would improve the game according to their skill level.
2. Prepare a written test using the rules and suggestions presented in this article.
3. Evaluate students' learning and the game itself, leaving students to write about how they felt while playing the game, what they learned, what they did not know before learning, how they would learn the collective game of handball (or specifically) a skill related to handball.
4. Get the teams to work together to create their own offensive and defense strategies.

Expected results

The results of this sports educational model should lead to the mastering of basic handball training, organized in the form of curricula, manuals and textbooks in handball. The methods adopted by teachers are based on the knowledge they have and use, as well as the belief in their effectiveness, often based on the life experience of the interviewed teacher. The little or no use of some methods, in turn, seems to us to be due to the fact that they are unknown to most of the teachers, rather than due to a lack of confidence in their effectiveness or disagreement on their ideological basis, which shows the needs of pedagogical updating of teachers working in higher education.

The results of research and development in the form of a product of sports education with basic movements in handball have the following advantages:

- 1) educating students to become athletes in the true sense, helping them grow, to become competent athletes, enthusiastic, wise and knowledgeable;
- 2) the model of sports education has goals that are immediate and comprehensive and must be achievable by students through their activity and participation;
- 3) supporting the activity of the handball teacher in optimizing the training through the model of sports education.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we would like to note that in recent years there has been great progress in all areas, including education, due to the high improvement of technology, improvements in communication and globalization of information. We hope that teachers in our field, as well as higher education institutions, are engaged and constantly looking for innovative ideas for education in order to accompany this evolution. Our ultimate goal is better preparation of future professionalists for work in the educational system, which is increasingly emerging with new characteristics. We believe that we have clarified the need for further research in the field of sports education with our proposed training model and we hope to encourage educators to better train in the discipline of Handball.

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